

Mario Pappagallo*

Executive Board Health City Institute, La Sapienza University, Rome, Italy

Received: 12 January, 2018

Accepted: 24 January, 2018

Published: 25 January, 2018

*Corresponding author: Mario Pappagallo, Executive Board Health City Institute, La Sapienza University, Rome, Italy, Tel: 3356508577; E-mail: mariopappagallo3@gmail.com

<https://www.peertechz.com>

Opinion

Get back in shape after the excess food with the secret of the Etruscans

Ancient advice (but scientifically modern) to help the body to regularize the metabolism, the biological clock, the use of fats and not to accumulate. Do not lose weight if you do not need it, but quickly get back to the right weight. Without drugs, without tricks.

Squeeze half a lemon in a liter of water to drink throughout the day. It is detoxifying, diuretic and you can drink up to two liters a day of this drink.

If you brush your teeth morning and evening, it is good to do it in the afternoon after lunch because the taste of food in the mouth will make you want to eat again in the evening.

In the Kitchen

Pepper helps digestion and therefore allows fat to burn more quickly. So, do not hesitate to pepper all your dishes well.

Parsley is diuretic, fights water retention and regulates the level of sugar in the blood. Use this slimming ally in your dishes daily.

Boil a handful of nettle leaves in half a liter of water to prepare a very effective slimming herbal tea to eliminate fat.

The cold potatoes develop the resistant starch, which satisfies without being assimilated in the form of fat. So do not hesitate to consume them like this.

The cooking water of artichokes (when they are there) certainly has a bitter taste, but has excellent diuretic properties. And above all it makes the liver work better, a key organ of

metabolism. Do not throw it and drink it to lose weight faster. An Etruscan recipe: six long leaves of artichokes, those that are thrown away at the market, boiled in a liter of water, filtered, bottled, drink a glass every morning fasting (with a little honey if too much bitter). This for a month a year, during the period of artichokes.

Crunching a raw tomato in the morning can help you lose weight faster by adjusting your cholesterol rate.

You know, in the evening you have to eat light. A legume soup will satisfy you and provide you with everything you need to resist until the following day.

Drinking green tea (or coffee) allows you to burn 80 extra calories a day.

In place of dairy products or desserts, eating a fruit after every meal is a good habit that will allow you to lose weight faster.

Sleep

Make yourself twelve hours of sleep without eating. In this way, during the evening and at night you will burn the fat reserves.

Beauty

Caffeine is considered a slimming component often used within slimming creams. In the same way, sprinkling the thighs with coffee grounds allows to streamline them.

Physical activity

An hour of housework makes you lose 200 calories. More to men.